

THE INFLUENCE OF THE DEDUCTIVE TEACHING AND GRAMMAR TRANSLATION METHOD ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF “FEEL FOR THE LANGUAGE” IN THE LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This research work investigates the grammatical errors made by an Uzbek secondary school learner in both spoken and written English, with a primary focus on subject-verb agreement. The participant was a 15-year-old ninth grade student whose English proficiency ranged from pre-intermediate to intermediate level. A descriptive research design was conducted by utilizing the Error Analysis approach. Data were collected through an interview and a writing task, analyzed as per the Surface Structure Taxonomy, which categorizes errors into omission, addition, and misformation. The findings uncovered that omission errors were the most frequent in both written (50%) and spoken (56%) production, followed by addition errors and a smaller proportion of misformation errors. The research work ascertained several possible causes of these errors, including first-language interference, insufficient exposure to communicative language use, and psychological factors such as anxiety and fear of speaking. Based on the findings, a communicative lesson plan was designed to address learners' challenges with subject verb agreement and enhance grammatical accuracy.

ВЛИЯНИЕ ДЕДУКТИВНОГО МЕТОДА ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ГРАММАТИКО-ПЕРЕВОДНОГО МЕТОДА НА РАЗВИТИЕ У УЧАЩИХСЯ «ЧУВСТВА ЯЗЫКА»

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ABSTRACT

Данное исследование рассматривает грамматические ошибки, допущенные узбекским

KEYWORDS

Анализ ошибок, грамматические ошибки, согласование подлежащего и сказуемого, таксономия поверхностной структуры, изучение английского языка, овладение вторым языком, ошибки пропуска, ошибки добавления, ошибки неправильной формы, коммуникативное обучение языку.

учащимся средней школы при использовании английского языка в устной и письменной формах, с основным акцентом на согласование подлежащего и сказуемого. Участником исследования был 15-летний ученик 9 класса, чей уровень владения английским языком варьировался от ниже среднего до среднего. Был применён описательный исследовательский дизайн с использованием метода анализа ошибок. Данные были собраны посредством интервью и письменного задания и проанализированы в соответствии с таксономией поверхностной структуры, которая классифицирует ошибки на пропуски, добавления и неправильные формы.

Результаты показали, что ошибки пропуска были наиболее частыми как в письменной (50%), так и в устной (56%) речи, за ними следовали ошибки добавления и меньшая доля ошибок неправильного образования форм. Исследование выявило несколько возможных причин данных ошибок, включая интерференцию родного языка, недостаточное воздействие коммуникативного использования языка, а также психологические факторы, такие как тревожность и страх говорения. На основе полученных результатов был разработан коммуникативный план урока, направленный на преодоление трудностей учащихся в области согласования подлежащего и сказуемого и повышение грамматической точности.

INTRODUCTION

Grammar plays inevitable role in second language acquisition since it assists in producing meaningful and accurate communication. Grammatical structure subject-verb agreement is considered as one of the fundamental and significant components which contributes to grammatical accuracy both in spoken and written discourse. Many English learners have challenges in applying this grammatical structure accurately despite its simplicity.

Error Analysis is a significant area of research in language teaching and learning as it assists in identifying learners' challenges and present actionable insights into the language acquisition process. Language teachers might identify the root causes of the errors and design applicable instructional strategies to eliminate those errors by assessing learners' errors constantly. Moreover, errors should not be perceived as failures since they might serve as indicators of learners'

developmental stages and progress in second language acquisition.

The primary objective of this study is to analyze and identify the learner's grammatical errors and investigate possible causes of these errors, and on the basement of the findings to formulate and propose effective pedagogical solutions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Subject -Verb agreement: The sentences are considered to be complete meaningful units. They do have a coordination among desperate parts of speech. This coordination between nouns and verbs is called Subject Verb Agreement or Subject Verb Concord. Learners always make certain errors in this grammatical point even though it seems to be easy for them. One of the basic rules of subject verb agreement is that a verb should agree in number and person with its subject. Singular subjects require singular verbs and plural subjects need plural verbs (Hudson, 1998).

There are three principles of subject-verb concord:

- Grammatical concord
- Notional concord (agreement in meaning)
- Proximity

Grammatical concord: Singular subjects always take singular verbs and plural subjects always take plural verbs. For instance, each girl has her own room.

Notional concord: The verb agrees with the subject according to notion of number. For example, fifteen miles seems like a long walk to me.

According to the proximity principle the verb agrees with the noun which precedes it. For example, Neither

students nor the instructor was agree with this idea.

Teaching problems and Learners' issues: There had been conducted many researches in identifying learners' grammatical problems and it was found that even advanced learners make more errors/mistakes in subject-verb agreement. Trainees make 95.5 % of the errors in this grammar point. Learning another language is based on habit formation. It was found that mother tongue is considered to be a barrier in acquiring foreign language. The hypothesis Contrastive Analysis also strengthened this view "Interference". Interference is when trainees' L1 influences negatively on their L2. Due to these habits, students cannot produce correct utterances and it consequently leads to the errors. On the other hand, Ehsan (1995) mentioned that similarities in syntactic structures between L1 and L2 can bring "positive transfer". Corder (1967) states that learners' mistakes/errors which are made in L2 are quite similar to the mistakes which are committed by a child learning his/her L1. This view is based on the concept LAD (Language Acquisition Device) which was developed by Noam Chomskiy. According to it children utilize their inborn universal structures. Concord (1967) emphasized that learners' errors can be considered as the signs/signals of their learning stages. He maintains that trainees' mistakes/errors are remarkable in three desperate ways:

1) errors are important for the teachers in selecting appropriate objectives

2) errors are notable for the learners since they can utilize them as a tool and eliminate them step by step

3) errors are remarkable for the researchers/linguists since they can understand second language acquisition;

Sanal (2008) also mentioned that errors should not be considered as “unwanted forms” as they might indicate about learners’ learning process level. In general, the sources of errors in language learning process are interlingual transfer and intralingual developmental errors. As it was aforementioned interlingual transfer is when L1 influences negatively on L2. Intralingual developmental errors refers to Target Language. Sanal (2008) mentions that errors are made due to learners’ lack of knowledge in the target language. Aforementioned learning problems/issues might be solid reasons for the participant to commit mistakes/errors in subject-verb agreement. However, there could be other reasons of the learner’s challenges in this grammar point. First, the utilization of wrong methods, approaches and activities might be the main reason. Participant mentioned that English lessons at school are only taught through Grammar-Translation method and Deductive approach. Grammatical rules are explained in Russian language and they learn new words in isolation. Students are given topics and they translate into Russian language. There is no focus on spoken production in the lessons which is considered to be an essential part of language learning process. It can be said that lessons at school are based on the accuracy rather than on fluency. Instructor utilizes teaching grammar as product approach.

Students are trained more through accuracy activities. Accuracy activities could bring counterproductive results if they are implemented wrongly. To be more precisely, learners should understand the meanings of the utterances in accuracy-based activities. If learners do not know/understand the meanings, it can cause negative results (Thornbury,2002).

In addition, psychological factors such as fear of making mistakes and anxiety might be the reason for making mistakes/errors in speech. It was observed that participant did not repeat the same mistakes/errors in her essay which she committed in her speech. Learner mentioned that she was afraid of to be recorded and it was noticeable that she felt anxiety in the interview. Affective Filter hypothesis is considered to be one of the five hypotheses of second language acquisition which was developed by Stephan Krashen. According to this hypothesis anxiety can raise affective filter and form “mental block” (Krashen, 1981). Consequently, learners start to make errors/mistakes.

METHODOLOGY

Learner that was selected for the research work is a teenager girl who studies at school in the 9th grade. She is 15 years old. Trainee is from Uzbek nationality. However, she prefers to speak Russian language since she studies in Russian class. The level of the participant is between pre-intermediate and intermediate level. Subject has been studying English intensively for a year. In current time, she practices mainly her speaking abilities through reading English novels and listening to the mini-stories of Allen Hoge.

This research project work was conducted in order to examine and identify the types of grammatical errors that were made by the participant both in her spoken and written production. There was selected error analysis technique and it was carried out in this research work. Error analysis technique was utilized to find exact errors faced by the learner. Research work is considered to be descriptive study by nature. Data was collected from the subject's interview. Writing test was also taken in order to triangulate the findings which were obtained from trainee's interview. There was utilized Surface Structure

Taxonomy Errors in order to analyze the data. The types of errors were researched thoroughly in order to have concise results.

FINDINGS

The outlined below types of errors were both in written and spoken production of the participant:

Omission: The absence of certain features

Addition: The presence of "unwanted forms"

Misformation: The utilization of wrong forms Surface Structure Taxonomy Errors

Table 1

Occurrence	Types of errors	Correct forms
So, lets' to introduce my personalities	Addition	my personality
I studied at school	Misformation	I study
These books interesting	Omission	These books are interesting
When I reading books in the fantasy genre	Addition	When I read ...
After I watching films	Addition	After watching ...
I watching films	Omission	I watch films
Madina very kind	Omission	Madina is very kind
My best friend it's Madina	Addition	My best friend is Madina
She always help	Omission	She always helps
She is always support	Addition	She always supports

Graph 1

The pie chart illustrates the percentage of the types of the errors which were committed by the participant. As is represented in the data the majority type of error is Omission which is 50% whereas Addition type of errors comes in the second place with 40%. Small proportion of the

errors/mistakes are Misformation errors which shows 10%. Then interview was taken in order to compare spoken and written types of the errors. The outlined below table and pie chart demonstrates the findings.

Table 2

Occurrence	Types of errors	Correct forms
I am studied	Addition	I study
My favorite lessons is matematics, Physics...	Misformation	My favorite lessons are
It tell story	Omission	It tells
We were studied	Misformation	We studied
I likes fantasy books	Addition	I like ...
She really hardworking	Omission	She is really hardworking
I reading books	Addition	I read books
I like a lot of types of book	Omission	I like a lot of types of books
My favorite book "Elene"	Omission	My favorite book is "Elena"
It really interesting	Omission	It is really interesting

Graph 2

The graph represents the percentage of three types of the errors: Addition, omission and misformation which were committed in spoken production of the participant. It is clear from gathered data that majority committed types of errors are Omission and Addition, which demonstrate 56% and 33% respectively whereas misformation errors comes in the last place with approximately 11%. It can be concluded that participant mostly made omission and addition types of errors in both written production and spoken production.

DISCUSSION

Most educational settings all over the world utilize Grammar Translation Method even though other methods/approaches have been developed so far. Instructors rely more on Deductive teaching approach and GTM since they are convenient for them. Consequently, learners suffer from this

wrong methodologies and approaches. Students work mainly on the accuracy yet they commit serious mistakes/errors both in their written and spoken production. Stephan Krashen quoted: "We teach the language best when we teach it for what it was designed for: Communication". For this reason, language should be taught by utilizing different approaches and methods.

Authenticity play an important role in language learning process and learners should be exposed to real language. Real language helps learners to acquire the language in context (Hillard, 2014). Stephan Krashen (1981) maintained that students acquire the language through listening and there should be created enough opportunities for the learners to practice the language.

The founder of "Effortless English System" Allen Hoge maintains (2014) that techniques and strategies play an

important role in language learning since they guide students in this challenging path. He proposed the “Movie Technique”. Students can train their speaking abilities at home. This strategy is very beneficial and has already showed its exceptional results. First and foremost, students are immersed in real language since they work on films. Learners practice and develop all areas of language acquisition:

- Spoken Grammar

- Expressions/Idioms in context
- Fluency/Accuracy
- Spontaneous speech
- “Feel” for the language
- Unconscious learning

The outlined below lesson plan was designed by incorporating different methods, strategies and theories on the basement of the findings in order to ameliorate learners’ “feel for the language”.

Lesson Plan

Tutor's name: Nilufar Shokirova	Date:
Grade: 9	Duration: 80 minutes
Subject/Unit: English Language	Level: Intermediate
Topic: Subject-Verb Agreement	
Type of the lesson: Practical	
Aims of lesson:	
<input type="checkbox"/> To ameliorate learners’ productive and receptive skills <input type="checkbox"/> To improve teamwork skills of trainees <input type="checkbox"/> To increase sensitivity of the learners to the forms of verbs and nouns <input type="checkbox"/> To enhance autonomous skills	
Lesson objectives: Students will be able to...	
<input type="checkbox"/> Utilize correct verb and noun forms <input type="checkbox"/> Learn the forms of verb and nouns in context	
Assumed prior knowledge: Trainees are students & does have background knowledge on this grammar point;	
Resources: Handouts, worksheets, Pictures of famous people, inspirational videos, cards, computer and projector, posters.	

Differentiation (addressing all learners' need):

Planned groups

Different learning styles-**Visual**-PowerPoint presentations & handouts; **Auditory**- watching a video, listening to a song, speaking individually, collaborating in group work, speaking based activities, reading based activity. **Kinesthetic**-Writing an essay

Skills for life/Key skills to be addressed:

Collaborating with other students in small groups; speaking individually; working in group and in pair, showing creativity and imagination, showing writing skills.

Types of assessments: Formative assessment, Formative assessment, Peer assessment

Instructional strategies: Guided practice, ICQ s & CCQs, Pair work, Individual work, Group work, discussion, evaluation, eliciting

Number/Numeracy of students: 10

Time	Content & Teacher Activity	Student Activity	Resource(s)
1 min	Introduction and explaining the content of the lesson	Watching & listening	No resources are required
5 min	Warm-up activity: Kahoot quiz. Asking students to enter https://kahoot.it/ and entering the pin which is on the screen	Individual work. Playing Kahoot quiz	Computer & projector Ten I pads or smartphones
15 min	Listening activity. Putting short inspirational video and distributing listening worksheets. Instructing them to fill the gaps while watching/listening. Asking learners to work in pairs and check/correct each other's answers. Encouraging them to think about the video and share their thoughts to their peer.	Filling the gaps with appropriate verb and noun forms while watching & listening (Individual work). Assessing each other's work and discussing the answers. Sharing thoughts about the video (Pair work)	Computer, projector & speakers Handout 1

15 min	<p>Reading activity. Dividing students into three equal groups and telling them to select one of the famous people which are shown on the screen. Instructing them to search for information about this famous person</p>	<p>Searching for the information about famous person. Reading attentively by highlighting useful expressions and useful words. Working on these new expressions and explaining these expressions to other teams on the white board (Group work)</p>	<p>Computer & projector Ten I pads/smartphones Handout 2 (Pictures of famous people)</p>
15 min	<p>Communicative activity. Giving each group pre-prepared posters of famous people accordingly. Telling them to write minimum 20 statements about famous person to the poster and highlight the forms of nouns and verbs. Instructing them walk around the classroom and leave feedbacks to other teams' posters after completing the task. Asking them to present their posters</p>	<p>Working in a group work and writing minimum 20 statements about famous person by utilizing acquired information and new expressions to the poster. Leaving the feedbacks to other teams' posters. Presenting poster</p>	<p>Handout 3 (Three posters)</p>
15 min	<p>Guided activity. Telling students to work individually and distributing each student cards with the names of famous people. Asking them to make up five questions about this famous person. Instructing them to work in pairs after completing the task and querying each other by utilizing created questions. Asking them to discuss the answers thoroughly and assess each other</p>	<p>Working individually. Making up five questions about famous person which is on the card. Then working in pairs and asking each other questions and discussing the answers. Assessing each other's answers</p>	<p>Handout 4</p>
20 min	<p>Writing activity. Telling students to choose one of the famous people and write small reflective essay about him for 15 minutes</p>	<p>Writing small reflective essay (Individual work)</p>	<p>Handout 5 (Worksheet)</p>

2 min	Explaining homework assignment and distributing assignment guidelines	Watching & Listening	No resources are required
<u>Homework/assignment set:</u> Selecting one of the famous people and creating a Facebook page about this famous person's life story		<u>Hand in date:</u>	

CONCLUSION

The lesson plan is specifically designed in order to eliminate most occurred subject-verb agreement errors in spoken and written production of the learners. Target learners of the lesson plan is intermediate learners. The ultimate goal of the lesson plan is to stimulate learners to notice noun and verb forms in context. For this reason, the combination of methods and approaches such as Think-Pair -Share, Inductive approach, CLT are implemented into the lesson plan. The learning styles of the learners is also taken into consideration by selecting appropriate activities/tasks in order to meet the needs of different trainees (Saman,2006). Desperate instructional strategies are included such as guided practice, ICQ/CCQs, pair work, group work, individual work. There is no single effective method in language teaching. And other aspects of language learning and teaching should be taken into consideration. Thus, several

principles and strategies of Kumaravadevilu are incorporated into the lesson plan:

- Maximize learning opportunities
- Integrate language skills
- Promote learner autonomy (Celce-Murcia, 2014)

Authentic materials ameliorate students' strong interest and motivation. There are created enough opportunities for them to acquire real language (Celce-Murcia, 2014). For this reason, authentic materials such videos, information about the life of famous people from the reliable internet sources are integrated.

The founder of Effortless English System Allen Hoge states the idea that learners' psychological blocks such as anxiety, fear of making mistakes, low self-esteem and self-confidence leads to "English trauma" which means inability of the learners to communicate despite many years of studying it. (Hoge,2014). Therefore, researcher tried to select strong inspirational video.

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